

MODERN IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS LESSONS ASPECTS OF USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *In this article, the principles of using modern pedagogical technologies in physical education and sports classes, their importance, the creation of a worldview and the scope of thinking, and some recommendations on the formation of physical, spiritual and moral qualities are discussed.*

Keywords: *sports, styles, activities, pedagogical technologies, feedback, control, methods, criteria, practical lessons.*

INTRODUCTION

The years of independence are literally spent with the implementation of large-scale reforms aimed at determining the perspective of the socio-economic and cultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, striving to take a worthy place among the countries of the world community. Studying the experiences of the developed countries of the world, taking into account local conditions, economic and intellectual resources, the implementation of fundamental reforms in all spheres of society ensures new achievements [1].

The sphere of physical culture and sports occupies the most important place in the socio-economic and cultural development of our people. Physical culture and sports as a social sphere educate people to become physically, mentally and spiritually mature and perfect individuals, economically and it contributes to the development of the production and economy of our country by restoring and strengthening the productive entities, i.e. people's health and high working abilities. As we know from history, the field of physical education and sports in every society serves the ideology of this society and develops under the influence of the ideology of this society. From the first days of independence, physical education has been the main factor in the education of a well-rounded generation by our state and the sports sector was given great attention and is a priority of state policy has become one of the directions, and even today, huge reforms are being carried out by our state.

The idea of national independence that is being formed in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan is to establish a humane, democratic, legal state and society, as well as to raise it to higher levels of socio-economic and cultural development, to take a worthy place in the ranks of the world community. serves to realize the directed noble goals.

The positive result of these goals is first of all the effective organization of educational and educational work to teach the young generation the basics of scientific knowledge, to create a broad outlook and scope of thinking in them, and to form physical, spiritual and moral qualities. depends on doing.

After all, creating a bright perspective of the country, spreading its name to the world, showing the national and cultural heritage created by the great ancestors to the society, enriching them, ensuring that the independent Republic of Uzbekistan occupies a place among the developed

countries, makes the young generation a perfect person in all respects and a qualified person. depends on training as a specialist.

Teachers should be prepared for conducting trainings, using various educational tools effectively, and should reveal the methodology of the curriculum and programs, integrating the teaching methods. However, do not forget that it is necessary to manage teaching and learning processes, to effectively use existing educational tools and to ensure that they are as useful as possible to students in educational activities, and many other similar tasks are the responsibility of the teacher fully loaded. The use of new pedagogical technologies in the teaching of subjects; the teacher is responsible for teaching and learning, as well as for the effective use of available opportunities and conditions. In order to fulfill this task, the teacher must study the teaching process and the scientific and technical aspects of the taught subjects should know fully.

The purpose of this is that the teaching method should be developed in such a way that students can fully master the taught subject.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

In determining whether teaching methods meet the needs of students, the teacher must consider the following six main components of his program:

1. Planning
2. Opportunity and conditions
3. Styles
4. Activities
5. Feedback
6. Control

One way to determine your teaching style is to make a list of questions that address each of the six factors listed above. It should be noted that ensuring the full fulfillment of the requirements of each component and following it increases the effectiveness of the chosen teaching method.

Planning; The teaching method includes:

- analysis of qualifications and main goals;
- composition of the group;
- necessary qualifications;
- subjects to be studied;
- motivating factors for learning;
- learning types and opportunities;
- educational material and its relevance to the times;
- the need to summarize experiences in identifying problems and finding solutions;
- the need for methods of presenting educational material;

The following conditions must be met for study:

- classrooms;
- educational tools;
- audio-video materials;
- various models and equipment;
- model weapons for practical training;
- assignments and tasks related to the topic;
- group or individual teaching methods;

- assessment materials.

Styles;

The teacher should be aware of the following teaching methods:

- teaching and giving instructions on how to perform the work;
- teaching using special computer programs;
- lecturing and teaching;
- demonstration and experiment;
- work on a project basis;
- use of algorithms and different analysis methods;
- study of the situation;
- role-playing, discussion and motivation exercises;
- teaching with the help of a computer.

For best results, use one of the following teaching methods can be achieved

- lecture;
- independent work;
- training based on audience demand;
- individual training;
- creating an opportunity to gain work experience.
- the teacher is not only a distributor of knowledge, but this be able to be a supplier of knowledge so that the listener can absorb it;
- organization of evaluation system;
- quick establishment of feedback between teachers and students.

Appropriate teaching and learning based on the criteria identified above

To develop the program, the teacher must be able to:

- having actual teaching skills;

Which of the following teaching methods is most effective?

- lecture;
- independent work;
- training based on audience demand;
- individual training;
- creating an opportunity to gain work experience.
- the teacher is not only a distributor of knowledge, but this be able to be a supplier of knowledge so that the listener can absorb it;
- organization of evaluation system;
- quick establishment of feedback between teachers and students.

In order to develop a suitable teaching and learning program based on the criteria defined above, the teacher should be able to:

- having actual teaching skills;
- to explain the criteria for determining the established norms for assessing the level of knowledge of students;
- determining the suitability of teaching methods for students.

RESULTS

Methods and means of increasing the efficiency of using modern pedagogical technologies, incorporating teaching methods in physical education and sports classes. Currently, physical education teachers, like all pedagogues, should organize lessons based on modern pedagogical requirements, requires the use of advanced pedagogical technologies, such as the formation of an innovative approach to the lesson, teaching students to think independently during the lesson.

Interactive method - by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process, it serves to activate the acquisition of knowledge and personal qualities of students in physical education and sports activities.

DISCUSSION

Interactive (interactive) is an English word, "interact" means "inter", mutual, "act" means "to act".

In general, "interactive" means to interact. differences between non-traditional and interactive lessons.

1. When teaching the subjects of the curriculum, it is necessary to take into account which subjects it is appropriate to organize interactive lessons.

In this case, to fully achieve the goal of training on one subject it is envisaged to use interactive or traditional types of training that provide

2. For the interactive training to be effective, the students are new before the training, it is necessary to ensure that they know the basic concepts and preliminary information on its topic.

3. It is necessary to take into account that more time is spent for independent work of students in interactive training than in traditional training.

Interactive education method is implemented by each teacher at the level of available tools and capabilities.

A physical education teacher can increase their knowledge and learning activity only if he knows the level of specific conditions of students.

To do this, prepare students for interactive training, it is necessary for them to master the taught topic, to be prepared for the training session, to be able to conduct discussions on the text read or listened to during the lesson, and to easily perform tasks of a creative and practical nature.

The educational process is not only a process controlled by the teacher, it is also closely connected with the students' activities.

The learning process is activated as a result of the student's self-management.

In physical education and sports lessons, the student can control his own behavior, identify and eliminate his mistakes, draw conclusions independently, participate in the performance of reproductive, partial research and creative tasks. , increases student activity and its implementation has an effective effect.

The advantage of using interactive methods in theoretical and practical lessons of physical education and sports:

1. In-depth learning of topics by students;
2. Ease of supervision of students by the teacher
3. Students get more information in a short time
4. Maximum development of students' skills and abilities,

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that interactive education provides an opportunity to solve several problems at the same time.

The main of these is that the communication skills and abilities of the students are developed, it helps to establish emotional relationships among the students, and the fulfillment of educational tasks by teaching them to work as part of a team, to listen to the opinions of their peers provides.

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